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ECO DESIGN AND CREATIVITY ISSUES

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ABSTRACT

Eco design research topics concerning methods, models and tools developed for early product development stages are considered in this paper. An overview of Eco design field is presented with an insight into Eco design methods and tools. The paper explores potential of Eco design tools for creativity uplift during concept development. The paper reviews the continuing challenges for boosting up creativity and innovation potential of developing eco-consciousness considering recent findings in creativity and eco-innovation.

Keywords: Eco design, early product development design phases, creativity

INTRODUCTION

Motivated by raised awareness on the importance of environmental issues and sustainable development, researchers in design community face a challenging task of developing solutions for incorporating environmental considerations of the products in redesign and new product development processes. Main contribution to designing more environmentally conscious products and processes is manifested in significant number of proposed Eco design tools. The significant part of these tools is used for establishing environmental impact of products (and product/service-systems) during product's life-cycle. Eco design tools tend to combine best characteristics of existing practices from design research findings and experiences from industry. Decomposing product's life-cycle into different stages in order to anticipate and simulate the environmental impact of each phase all over the product's lifespan, e.g. life-cycle thinking approach (Abele et al., 2005) has been one of the major

concerns throughout a two-decade-old distinct research discipline in the field of engineering design commonly known as Eco design. Research has delivered contribution to design community and industry alike, and is currently focusing on the issues of systematically introducing developed approaches and philosophies (with life-cycle thinking approach dominant at this point), guidelines, methodologies, frameworks, models and tools to industry practice and inducing the processes of sustainable business creation (McAloone, 2009). Eco design today is acknowledged in the research community and equally important in industry. Eco design tools have been introduced as a part of everyday routine in companies. Feedback from industry on practicing Eco design additionally enhances researches. Routine usage of environmental impact assessment tools in developing environmentally conscious solutions, and life-cycle planning (Life Cycle Design) as an upward trend has been reported in numerous papers on Eco design workshops held at conferences like ICED, DESIGN and alike. Eco design in general is tasked to aid the process of design optimization for reducing product's impact on the environment that is assumed to contribute to global warming, waste over-generation problem, problems of reducing hazardous substances and uncalled for effects of distinct environmental blazing problems and issues.

PORTRAYING ECO DESIGN FIELD

Starting as a young and interdisciplinary research field resulting in a (for the time being) lack of journals specifically devoted to this subject, from a group of opportunistic eco-pathfinders trying to optimize product's recyclability, Eco design has expanded considerably as an acknowledged scientific research area (Boks & McAloone, 2008). When Eco design (sometimes referred to as ecodesign, Design

for Environment or Design for Sustainability) emerged in the last decade of 20th century, significant change occurred, since its commitment was oriented towards transforming prevailing end-of-pipe design process approach to the pollution prevention approach. Common assumption was that by changing product concepts and thus associated inputs and production processes, it is possible to avoid or at least reduce the generation of waste and the cost of abatement. First observations on the field regarding this premise lead to conclusion that life-cycle philosophy is prevailing among the research community. Life-cycle thinking depicts Eco design way of thinking. It is not uncommon to claim that Life Cycle Design (life-cycle approach in general, which is defining life-cycle stages in a distinctive way and analyzing product's environmental load in every stage independently) moulds Eco design scene and practice, from tools to frameworks. Definitions of Eco design equally evoke and regularly consider life-cycle approach as leading strategy for coping with environmental considerations of product development and issues connected to one of the product's universal virtues - environmental effects, as well as and few other sub-topics as environmental impact assessment and related indicators, Design for X, eco-innovation, etc. The situation at the beginning of two-decade-long tradition of the field seemed in drawback status because of lack of opportunities for getting scientific articles published in high rating journals and specialized journals reserved for sustainability and environmental design issues not been initiated yet, lead Eco design focus to directing more on the industry and what the industry needed. Eco design is today well acknowledged in the research community and more important in the industry practice. Subsequently, more on this claim is to be found while recapitulating Eco design research assets - Eco design tools. For example, none of the Eco design tools was so embraced by a wider circle of scientists, engineers and other interested stakeholders in the community as the LCA methodology. The last decade of late century brought environmental requirements to product development at a large scale and thanks to raise of interest in product life-cycle management issues. The strength of LCA analysis has overgrown its initial task and became a language of understanding

between interdisciplinary experts involved in product development process inside the company and in external chains of organization of the company to market and back. As all the stakeholders have found the universal methodology of analyzing and predicting environmental impact of product's output in product development process stages compliant to what they lacked of in traditional project layouts, similar environmental impact assessment methods began to infiltrate into industry practice leading to development of new and improvement of existing methods. LCA (Life Cycle Assessment) revealed several tool characteristics that seemed to be highly valuable; since it serves the purpose of elaborately, explicitly and quantitatively expressing environmental impact of observed product during all stages of its lifespan and what is interesting for the subtheme of this paper, seems to be a viable support for decision-making purposes (Miyamaru & Kulay, 2006).

Apart from LCA that has been standardized in the meantime (ISO 14000 series), it is often misplaced that a great number of other Eco design tools, including guidelines, environmental impact assessment methods and many more, differentiating in scope, product development phase implementation, quantitative and qualitative depiction of results in form of diagrams and matrices has been frequently reviewed in current Eco design research publications. What is noticeable is lack of reports on 'diffusion' of Eco design tools when they are implemented in everyday industry practice, so there is a tendency to promote systematical integration of environmental considerations in product design development processes. Feedbacks from industry on practicing Eco design additionally enhance researches and in some cases reports have been made on environmental related criteria considered a routine procedure for various purposes into developing environmentally conscious solutions. Also, it is noticeable that some environmental assessments can not be conducted by designers themselves, but experts are called for have been conducted by experts (called for example Eco design experts, from the centre of expertise) because of the time-consuming, data-consuming and some other issues dealing with complexity of procedures needed for environmental assessment

methods or product complexity burdens. Environmental related data, criteria and methods procedures are subject of changes, upgrades and improvements. These fluctuations are to be followed, data updated and case to case approach is often necessary (Andriankaja et al., 2009). Because of the need for tools and approaches that would supply stakeholders with the environmental related information regarding gas emissions, embodied energy, waste and recycling quantities and strategies, material selection and so forth, development of existing and new tools, methods and approaches continues and seems to leave some casualties. Referring to the European Commission's succinct definition of what is Eco design all about: 'Eco-design aims to improve the environmental performance of products throughout the life-cycle by systematic integration of environmental aspects at a very early stage in the product design,' not so many Eco design tools can assist designers in early stages of product development process, although it is often been emphasized that early stages of the product development process are decisive in terms of product cost reduction and product development process cost and resources acquired optimization.

MOTIVATION

In context of commonly perceived product development processes model or classical PDPs (Lindeman & Lorenz, 2008), early design stages are often stated to be decisive, since most impact on definition and structure of the product developed takes place previous to detailing and embodiment phases. There are also some important findings that environmental considerations about the products needs to be taken as important criteria (for example in form of environmental requirements) when planning, task definition or requirements setting activities are on-the-go. These claims are been taken into consideration by several authors invoking integration of Eco design in earliest design stages as a preferable situation (Sherwin, 2000). Conceptual design phase has not been neglected in that sense, but is obvious that a considerable small number of Eco design tools are applicable as a support for the concept design development activities. Some of the reasons for this are in the lack of knowledge about the product at this stage of product development

process according to (Lindahl, 2006). Although, considerable efforts have been made on development of methods and tools for concept evaluation that would include environmentally related data about the concepts being developed (Feroli et al., 2008) and decision-making purposes (Kengpol & Bookanit, 2010; Hallstedt et al., 2010), it is found that Eco design tools merely present in industry practice (for environmental impact assessment purposes) cannot be adapted for conceptual design development activities (Collado-Ruiz & Ostad-Ahmad-Ghorabi, 2011). (O'Hare et al., 2009) explains the situation as a non-surprising consequence of lack of uptake of Eco design tools and eco-innovation tools, related to the nature and purpose of those tools and practices.

SUPPORT FOR INCORPORATING ECO DESIGN IN EARLY PRODUCT DEVELOPMENT PHASES

PRODUCT DEVELOPMENT PROCESS - THE CONCEPTUAL DESIGN PHASE OUTLINE

Product development process in its generalized description is a sequence of phases, steps or activities starting from planning of product or product/service system, followed by concept development phase, embodiment (system-level design and detail design following. Ulrich and Eppinger (Ulrich & Eppinger, 2004) when describing a concept development process often state that no matter what type of product development model is incorporated, every product development process possesses a front-end character; sequence of steps or activities for product realization. A product concept is an approximate description of the technology, working principles and form of the product. It is a concise description of how the product will satisfy the customer needs and consequently - design specifications. Concept generation is an integral part of the concept development phase. Pahl and Beitz (Pahl & Beitz, 1988) systematic approach procedural plan of product development process, sets the conceptual design phase to follow the clarification of the task put in front of the designer or team members included in the product development process.

Embodiment design is the part of the design process in which, starting from the principle solution or

concept of a technical product, the design is developed in accordance with technical and economic criteria and in the light of further information, to the point where subsequent detail design can lead directly to production. Andreasen and Hein (Andreasen & Hein, 2000) also state that queues of events in product design activity plans and ongoing development trial is known (Integrated product development) and this can be the very thing to either boost or stem the project (product development process) in terms of finding and developing creative, innovative or more desirable outcome.

Figure 1. Concept generation process selected out from (Ulrich & Eppinger, 2004)

HOW TO DEAL WITH ENVIRONMENTAL REQUIREMENTS IN PRODUCT DEVELOPMENT?

Product development process with various requirements and specifications determining/establishing the task definition could be seen as an optimization process for solving the problem task, design problem or other, between sometimes conflicting targets. Finding a certain material for the exact price and quantity to suit and accomplish a certain function of the given part or assembly is difficult enough. Now, additionally adding the environmentally conscious priority (e.g., considering the energy to produce the material, but also considering material recycling capability of the material), may become an unavailing task. Common to most development processes is a certain sequence of developing product specifications first, then deriving the functional structure and using creativity techniques to develop several possible product concepts before one concept is selected for embodiment design aided by evaluation and assessment procedure, tool or model.

Introducing environmental thinking in the early phase of product development is most important, according to authors in Eco design research field. When laying down the product specifications, planning stage and activities precedent to estimating design targets should be on board already.

Environmental target values sorted should be understood by the design team. This is essential in order to come up with a good overall environmental performance of the product being developed. But the question is how to derive the correct environmental targets for a certain product? Wimmer et al. (2008) state the importance of understanding environmental impacts of the product through its life-cycle via detailed analysis of the product life-cycle data that will substantiate environmental profile of the product and environmental evaluation of the concepts, e.g. product put to market. The research describes six steps of developing green product concepts. Main attribution of the work consists of marking the systematic thinking policy as a strategy (or product improvement strategy) for coping with unwanted complexity of the parameters involved in the product realization process.

DECISION MAKING AND CONCEPTS EVALUATION AND SELECTION

Aside from environmental benchmarking (Stevens, 2004) and similar analysis Eco design tools for setting out environmental requirements and establishing target environmental performance values (planning and project task definition product development phase), scientific efforts have also been made to include environmental considerations in product development processes regarding decision-making activities and integrating environmental considerations into decision support systems. These can be bristly divided into three groups:

- Eco design tools for qualitative and/or quantitative environmental impact assessment that serve as criteria for evaluating and decision-making purposes,
- Researches on implementing Eco design tools in product development process as stand-alone decision support system that includes environmental impact assessment analysis related criteria,
- Systematic or robust frameworks with embedded decision support system module that can either integrate environmental impact assessment tools (Eco design tools) or specific environmental related criteria or methods.

More recent work on decision-systems support including environmentally related data in the data collection for product development planning phase can be found in (Hallstedt et al., 2010). An approach to assessing sustainability integration in strategic decision systems for product that Kengpol and Bookanit propose (Kengpol & Bookanit, 2010) makes an exceptional view of a conceptual phase decision-making process, where concepts are submitted to trial of evaluation, often multi-objectively, meaning that are rated on a greater number of criteria and/or submissive to abundance of methods for concept evaluation and selection.

AFFILIATION OF ECO DESIGN AND ENGAGING TOPICS CONCERNING CREATIVITY AND ECO-INNOVATION

DESIGN CREATIVITY AND ECO DESIGN INTERFERENCE ISSUES

Actual trends tempting the designers nowadays, do not explicitly state that environmental effects of the products are crucial for concept definition and development since there are more relevant things to think of before concepts' eco-value when product's market and commercial success is estimated prior to concept product release. New ideas, concepts and creativity of involved actors are challenged by the sustainability performance criteria, although not in an explicit way. Eco-performance thus comprehends life-cycle approach of product development process and suitable calculated value either by LCA or other tools for calculating product's environmental load or impact. This means a lot of engaging and time-consuming work. So, in its basic definition - developing eco-friendly products does not include creativity techniques, methods or tools. In other words, environmental preferences leave no room for creativity vent in any phase of the product development process.

In the work of (Collado-Ruiz & Ostad-Ahmad-Ghorabi, 2011) qualitative environmental assessment in innovation projects including environmental criteria is not effective, but they are optimistic on developing evaluation methods that would not suppress, but boost creativity and make more eco-consciousness concepts for further embodiment and

detail design development and in the end environmental friendlier products.

Commonly accepted definition of creativity is that creativity is the ability to generate new useful things that are characterized by being original and imaginative (Shai et al., 2009). More terms to describe ideas, concepts or products as creative include usefulness and appropriateness. Vast number of the general definition interpretations, diverge the research on the topic to disciplinary fields dealing with cognition, social and behavioral psychology, psychometrics, artificial intelligence, philosophy, history, economics, business and management. From the selected themes from Design Creativity Special Interest Group 2010 publication - SIG Design Creativity (Taura & Nagai, 2011) a conclusion can be derived: bringing together eminent authors, discerning conclusions and future researches in the field of design creativity - new ideas on these topics will raise from interdisciplinary interlocking different research fields and disciplines, for example: engineering design, industrial design, artificial intelligence, linguistics and cognitive science disciplines. Previous to recent publication in the case of (Howard et al., 2008) a momentum to conduct cross disciplinary research was identified based on engineering design and creativity literature from cognitive psychology. This intriguing proposal tends to combine research dealing with the development of creativity potential each individual human being possesses and the knowledge and understanding on design and design processes from the designer himself. While in the domain of engineering design terms design problem, design process and design team are connoted, in psychology and congenial domains, creative processes is a subject to study as well as means of supporting creativity which are something worth adopting to bypass routine design solutions. The impression given by authors interested in engineering design and cognitive psychology synergy of associated methods and interpretations of design processes is that the future of innovative, novel, original and visionary design solutions is somewhere in the cross section of these two domains and can be achieved through close interdisciplinary team collaboration.

ECO-INNOVATION

Innovation is nowadays seen as one of the most relevant factors of obtaining commercial and market share interests resulting ensuing business success for product developing industries, and a ticket for SMEs to gain substantial competitive advantage. McAloone considers innovation as the 3rd most important motivator for industry to involve in research, development and implementation of Eco design tools and in that way transforming their goods to be greener (thus more attractive for the customers), eco directive and regulations compliant and transform their production technology and process into less invasive for the environment (McAloone, 2009). Although greening of products is not solely factor that will guaranty commercial success of the products in the competitive market environment, insisting on sustainable product innovation offers opportunities for the company to discover creative potential inside the company, redesign their production processes and consider different EOL strategies that can lead to less waste or at least be a step further from end-of-pipe policy to life-cycle approach.

CONCLUSION

The opinions prevailing throughout the paper are founded upon the identified necessity of incorporating Eco design as early in the product development process. The paper argues the circumstances leading to lack of appropriate methods, models and tools that can be incorporated in the conceptual design development stage particularly, since quality, cost and market success of final products are first determined at concept design level. The focus was to establish is there room for improvement of product concepts (either their ecologically acceptability or creativity increase potentials of product or their development processes) regarding the outcomes of exercising Eco design and eco-innovation in early design product development stages, especially conceptual design stage since this is where creative input is most expected from participants involved.

The questions regarding what happens when tendency towards developing more environmentally conscious solutions, concepts and finally products comes across innovation and creativity stipulations

are also arisen in this paper. Emerging research will have to include more comprehensive literature overview since interdisciplinary approach requires a more broad perspective to the research questions which are as follows:

1. Which creativity methods can be helpful for incorporating Eco design methods and tools in early product development design stages?
2. Can any of the existing Eco design methods and tools be altered to help boosting the creativity of design processes and product concepts?
3. How could environmental requirements set for products and product development processes become more vital for the company, designers and customers?

Dominant Eco design approaches to date tend to focus on environmental impact estimations and resource use in production. Awareness about the consequences of disregarding the life-cycle of designed products or product/service systems has been increased since the responsibilities of the designers and engineers involved in the product development process have been demystified and some Eco design methods standardized. It seems that despite the progress of making sustainable design more familiar both to designers and customers, target commercial value of the product and some other product properties, still take advantage over product's environmental impact value. General assumption is that this will remain to be in pat position until direct demand for green products will be identified from the customers and subsequently the market.

This paper points at observing Eco design in the early phases of the product development process. Despite Eco design implementation 'stallers', there is room for breakthrough in this area and allow for creativity design research and new methods and tools developed to be incorporated in existing or new product development processes.

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